

1 **CDK4 is activated in central nervous system metastasis in human breast cancer.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 East Islip, NY USA 11730

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 We report here the identification of CDK4 as a viable therapeutic target in human breast cancer
7 featuring metastasis to the central nervous system (CNS). CDK4 was retrieved as an up-regulated and
8 differentially expressed kinase using whole transcriptome technology that measures and compares total
9 transcription in human breast cancers (the primary tumor) and in the CNS metastases of humans with metastatic
10 breast cancer. Overall survival (the amount of time from diagnosis until death) was 3 years (36.33 months)
11 greater in humans with breast cancer whose tumors expressed low levels of CDK4 as compared to patients
12 whose tumors expressed high levels of CDK4; this was statistically significant. We have already utilized
13 multiple whole transcriptome technologies to predict and demonstrate a likely and strong therapeutic benefit in
14 humans with hormone receptor positive (HR+) cancer (luminal A and luminal B subtypes). These data indicate
15 patients with existing CNS metastasis are also likely to benefit from adjunctive pharmacologic CDK4/6
16 inhibition from the -ciclib family (palbociclib, ribociclib and abemaciclib).

Figure 1: CDK4 is differentially expressed and up-regulated in human breast cancer.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1019	1.04E-03	0.2335	-3.2804941	-0.76600047	2194.85	CDK4	2533/21403	88.2

Figure 2: Low CDK4 tumor expression is significantly correlated with superior overall survival.

Chart 1: Overall survival in humans with breast cancer, with low or high CDK4 expression.

High expression: 110.4 months (median)

Low expression: 74.07 months (median)

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Methods

We utilized RNA-sequencing from GSE191230 (*n*=8 primary tumors (breast tumors from humans with breast cancer) vs. *n*=5 brain metastases (CNS metastases from humans with breast cancer) for this study. We used human survival data from *n*=1880 humans with breast cancer for this study.

Supplemental data

S1: CDK6 is weakly induced but not differentially expressed in CNS metastases of humans with breast cancer.

<u>GeneID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FC</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
1021	7.52E-01	0.602	-0.3163468	-0.19043774	396.03	CDK6	18481/21403	13.7